

Rethinking Family: Cultural Perspectives on Childlessness and the Married Couple Experience

Mina Margaret Ogbanga, PhD

Abstract

The study examined the cultural perceptions of childlessness towards married couples in the society. One objective and one research question were raised for the study. The descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. A population of 160,301 women in 65 communities in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State was used. A sample of 100 women from 5 communities was used and this was done via multi-stage sampling technique of Random sampling technique and Proportionate sampling technique. The questionnaire titled "Socio-cultural Impact of Childlessness on Married Couples Questionnaire (SICMCQ)" was used as instrument to collect relevant data. The instrument was validated by some experts and its reliability was tested for to be 0.75. The data collected, were analyzed using frequency, mean and percentage for the research questions and Chi-square was used to test for the hypotheses. The findings from the study showed that the mean responses of the women on the cultural perceptions of childlessness towards married couples in the society. From the analysis done, all the items with respective mean scores of 3.28, 3.04, 3.08 and 3.05 were accepted because their mean scores are above the criterion-mean score of 2.5. Based on the grand mean score obtained at 3.11, it can therefore be deduced that there is a high level of negative cultural perception attributed to childlessness of married couples in the society.

Introduction

Childlessness has varied consequences through its effects on societies and on the lifestyles and life chances of individuals. The childless lifestyle enhances life satisfaction for some individuals, while diminishing it for others, for whom parenthood was a personal goal (Rasak&Oladipo, 2017). For societies, childlessness is a factor in low birth rates and population decline, with which are associated diminishing labour force entries and rising proportions in older ages. Childlessness is therefore a consideration for policy makers, both because of its demographic impact and because of its effects on the lives of individuals. The latter become most apparent in the older ages, where childlessness means that family resources for support of the disabled or frail are less assured. Childlessness significantly impacts a couple's marriage and become a greater contributor of stress than any other life problem. Women are left with feeling empty, defective, incomplete, undesirable and unworthy (Obiyo, 2016). In turn, some couples find it necessary to endure the pain of childlessness through social isolation in order to protect themselves. As a result of the loneliness experienced, couples with childlessness often

have difficulty expressing their feelings of sorrow and most often grieve in private because they feel as though no one can truly understand their feelings of despair and hopelessness. There is an uncomfortable silence around the issue of childlessness in our Nigerian society. It is often tough enough to lend an ear to the laments of those who experience such pain, suffering and indignity when it comes to the scourge of barrenness. It can be even more grueling for those who suffer from childlessness. Thus childlessness can be a traumatic and worrying experience for men and women who for cultural or personal reasons, view childbearing as central to their life (Dierickx, Rahbari, Longman, *et al.*, 2018). This is because fertility is one of the most intimate areas of human existence in our Nigerian society. It reaches deep into an individual's membership of the human race, as well as their place in the extended family.

Childlessness is an important and growing phenomenon and has increasingly become the focus of research by [sociologists](#) and policy makers, primarily in Western Europe. As McAllister and Clarke (2000: p. 189) point out, "as the average age of motherhood has increased in many Western societies, the issue of distinguishing between those who postpone parenthood and those who renounce it altogether has become of key interest."

Historically, childlessness is not new. It was quite common until the early part of the twentieth century. According to Wrigley and Schoefield (1983), in eighteenth-century England, up to one quarter of women remained unmarried and the majority of these had no children. However, in the past, childlessness among married women was primarily due to poverty and consequent malnutrition. Childlessness today (see, for example, Dykstra and Hagestad, 2007), while similar in magnitude, is very different from the past. It occurs among healthy, sexually active women who live in relative prosperity. The prevalence of lifetime childlessness has been shown by demographers to be far from uniform both within and between countries, and according to Coleman (1993), it is likely to generate considerable differences in fertility levels. While exact figures are difficult to obtain, many sources provide differing estimates and projections of current trends suggesting that in many countries from one-fifth to one-quarter of women will remain childless throughout their lifetimes (Eurostat, 1997; Morgan and Chen, 1992; Coleman, 1998; Rowland, 2007). In addition to Germany, England and Wales, Canada, Finland, and Austria, this includes various Eastern European countries (Coleman, 1998). Researchers agree that primary infertility cannot account for this level of childlessness (Rindfuss *et al.*, 1988; Ruthstein and Shah, 2004; Vaessen, 1984).

Aim and Objective of the Study

To assess the cultural perceptions of childlessness towards married couples in the society.

Research Question

What are the cultural perceptions of childlessness towards married couples in the society?

Significance of the Study

To sociologists; the findings from this study will bring forth the weightiness of childlessness on married couples thereby engendering them to developing encouraging mechanisms to help them strive hard on this without being stressed or discouraged.

Scope of the Study

This study will strictly focus on examining socio-cultural and childlessness impact on married couples in the society. The target population for this study will comprise of married couples in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Definition of Terms

Childlessness: This refers to the inability of procuring an offspring.

Impact: This refers to the exacerbated influence an entity has on another.

Socio-Cultural Impact: This refers to the influence exerted by the society on another entity socially and culturally.

Married Couples: These are individuals that have decided to imbibe the duty of coming together to live as one legally, traditionally or religiously.

Cultural Perception towards Childlessness of Married Couples in the Society

In the African culture, the true meaning of marriage is only fulfilled if the couple conceives and bears children (Ojedokun, 2019). Africans consider their child to be a source of power and pride, and children act as insurance for their parents in old age. The most important aspect of bearing children is an assurance of family continuity. Anthropological and sociological studies bear testimony to the considerable suffering associated with involuntary childlessness due to negative psychosocial consequences such as marital instability, abuse and stigmatization (Gouni, Jarašiūnaitė-Fedosejeva, KömürcüAkik, *et al.*, 2022). A study among women seeking infertility treatment in Southern Ghana revealed that infertile women used their internal coping strategies by keeping their fertility problem to themselves as a result of the stigma associated with it whilst others coped by drawing on their Christian faith. Children are deemed important in African communities due to the fact that they are the ones who carry on family names as well as keep the lineage running. They also inherit family properties and are expected to procreate to replace departed members” (Anokye, Acheampong, Mprah,*et al.*, 2017). In the context of religion, children are seen as divine gift from God and inability to conceive may be seen as resulting from a sin or being unworthy of God’s gift. The issues surrounding infertility in Nigeria are problematic in nature because of the mystique associated with them. This may be because childbearing is viewed as a natural part of adult life in traditional African setting. For example, infertility has been labelled an act of God, a punishment from unhappy ancestors, or the result of witchcraft. Procreation in marriage is central in traditional African setting, its absence means an insult to both the man and woman and further threatens the acuity of masculinity and femininity and cause psychological stress (Wando, 2017). In addition, because of the unanticipated nature of involuntary childlessness, couples normally perceive a loss of a primary life goal, hence, their reaction in most circumstance is the same with other people experiencing a crisis. Some of such reactions include denial, anger, isolation, guilt and depression. Furthermore, because of the much

premium placed on children in traditional African setting. It is also believed that inability to conceive is associated with many psychological reactions such as anxiety, shame, grief, social loneliness and self-blame in couples (Audu, Takim, Edem, *et al.*, 2013).

Review of Related Empirical Studies

Rasak and Oladipo (2017) in their study sought to investigate Childlessness and Its Socio-Cultural Implication on Married Couples within Some Selected Yoruba Communities in South-West Nigeria. Descriptive survey method was adopted for the study. Questionnaire was used for data collection. It was found out that not having children, whether voluntarily or not, contributes to a kind of invisibility and poverty in Nigeria. It concluded by noting a more tolerant attitude to in voluntary childlessness and then suggesting possible changes in perceptions of the condition.

Egharevba (2020) in a study examined the relationship between childlessness and social cultural impact among married couples in Egor Local government Area of Edo state. Cross-sectional research design was adopted for the study. A sample of 100 respondents was chosen for the study via random sampling technique. It was revealed therein that the existence of a relationship between childlessness and social incompatibility; which often result in separation and/or abandonment of wives in the community, poor communication among married couples; lack of knowledge on adoption; and other socio-cultural consequences, including abuse on the woman, social stigma, and divorce. It was then recommended among others that the Social Welfare Department should intensify awareness campaign on adoption; such information should be complemented by community advocacy and mobilization through the media, as well as Healthcare Providers playing their role in counseling. Anokyeet *al.* (2017) in a study sought to determine the psychosocial effects of infertility among couples attending St. Michael's hospital, Jachie-Pramso. Descriptive study design was adopted for the study. A sample of 100

respondents was chosen for the study via simple random technique. Questionnaire was employed for data collection. It was revealed therein that the social effects of infertility on couples included exclusion, verbal and physical abuse, divorce as well as stigma. It was also revealed therein that there is high level of despondence among couples who are considered infertile. It was then concluded that infertility has psychological, emotional and social consequences on individuals as well as couples. It was therefore recommended that families should support infertile individuals in every way that they can so that they will not be isolated. Arowosegbe *et al.* (2019) in a study sought to investigate the effect of childlessness on marital satisfaction among married couples in Ado-Ekiti L.G.A of Ekiti State. Descriptive survey design was utilized for the study. A sample of 200 participants was used for the study via random selection method. Questionnaire was employed as data collection instrument. Based on the findings, conclusions were made that from the results of this research, that there is no significant influence of age on marital satisfaction and that there is a significant influence of childlessness on marital satisfaction.

Methodology

Research Design

The design of this study is the descriptive research design. This design is that which employs both qualitative and quantitative data for the proper dissemination of the stated questions that are formulated to dissolve the major purpose for this study. This research design was chosen because of the purpose of the study to gather information on socio-cultural impact of childlessness on married couples in the society.

Population of the Study

The population for this study will comprise of women present in the 65 communities in Obio-Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State, which constitutes to a total estimation of 160,301 women (National Population Census, (2008) and World Sex Ratio (2021)).

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

A multi-stage sampling technique of random sampling technique and proportionate sampling technique will be used for sample selection. Random sampling technique will be used in the selection of 5 communities out of the 65 communities in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State. Proportionate sampling technique will then be adopted in the selection of 20 women each in the chosen communities. A total sample of 100 women will then be given and used for the study, as stipulated in the table below:

Table 1: Sample Distribution

S/N	Districts	Sample Chosen
1	Choba	20
2	Rumueme	20
3	Ozuoba	20
4	Rumuokoro	20
5	Rumuigbo	20
Total		100

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument employed in this study is the questionnaire. It is a 20-item self-structure instrument titled **“Socio-cultural Impact of Childlessness on Married Couples**

Questionnaire (SICMCQ)” that will be partitioned into two sections (A and B). Section A will cover the demographic aspect of it, which collects personal information about the respondents, while section B will cover the items, which elicited the responses of the respondents on each of the item statements present. The items are responded to with the aid of 4-point Likert scale of measurement of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD).

Method of Data Collection

Data will be collected using questionnaires. The researcher will go to the field and meet up with respondents, then hand out the copies of the questionnaire to them. These respondents will be given directives on how to go about the filling of the distributed instrument. After completion, the researcher will proceed to retrieve the distributed instrument immediately.

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

Face and content validity of the instrument will be established by giving it to my supervisor and two other lecturers in the Department of Sociology. Their inputs will be ratified further by the supervisor, before its incorporation in the production the final draft of the questionnaire. The reliability of the instrument will be done through the test-retest method. This method is that which involves the administration of the instrument to a selected group of 20 women (outside the sample of the study but within the population of the study) with a separating time difference of 10 days between the two administrations. The responses gotten from the two administrations will then be compared and correlated through the adoption of Pearson Product Moment Correlation, so as to arrive at the reliability co-efficient index of 0.75.

Method of Data Analysis

The data will be subjected to an analytical procedure with the aid of frequency, mean and percentage for the research questions. Chi-square will be used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The criterion-mean will be calculated for as follows:

Strongly Agree (SA) - 4points

Agree (A) - 3points

Disagree (D) - 2points

Strongly Disagree (SD) - 1point

$$\text{Criterion mean} = \frac{4+3+2+1}{4} = \frac{10}{4} = 2.5$$

The item with a mean score that is up to and above the criterion mean will be “accepted” while the one with a mean score that is below the criterion mean will be “rejected”.

Results and Discussion

Results

Demographic Analysis

Table 2: Frequency and percentage of the demographics of women

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
20-29yrs	30	30%
30-39yrs	45	45%
40-49yrs	25	25%
50yrs & above	0	0%
Marital Status		
Single	25	25%

Married	55	55%
Divorced	15	15%
Widowed	5	5%
Separated	0	0%

From the analysis done above, it was displayed that 30% of the total sampled women are of 20-29yrs, 45% of the total sampled women are of 30-39yrs, 25% of the total sampled women are of 40-49yrs; 25% of the total sampled women are single, 55% of the total sampled women are married, 15% of the total sampled women are divorced while 5% of the total sampled women are widowed.

Research Question 3: What are the cultural perceptions of childlessness towards married couples in the society?

Table 3: Mean statistics displaying the cultural perceptions of childlessness towards married couples in the society

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	Remark
9	Childlessness is not a divine agreement between God and us.	38 (152)	52 (156)	10 (20)	0 (0)	3.28	Accepted
10	Childlessness is not to be beheld in the African culture.	30 (120)	48 (144)	18 (36)	4 (4)	3.04	Accepted
11	Childlessness is traditionally not accepted as a norm that can happen.	32 (128)	49 (147)	14 (28)	5 (5)	3.08	Accepted

12	Childlessness shows a weakened state of the original purpose of man on earth.	29	51	16	4		
		(116)	(153)	(32)	(4)	3.05	Accepted
	Grand Mean					3.11	High

Data in the table above displayed the mean responses of the women on the cultural perceptions of childlessness towards married couples in the society. From the analysis done, all the items with respective mean scores of 3.28, 3.04, 3.08 and 3.05 were accepted because their mean scores are above the criterion-mean score of 2.5. Based on the grand mean score obtained at 3.11, it can therefore be deduced that there is a high level of negative cultural perception attributed to childlessness of married couples in the society.

Recommendations

- 1) Proper awareness should be given to couples as to the factors that are inherent to cause childlessness for them.

- 2) .It can help in the diagnosing of potent factors as well as strategies that can be linked to the issue of childlessness among couples in the society.

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